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Impostor Phenomenon as a Predictor of Performance and Work Outcomes Among Employees

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ABSTRACT

Suppose you are at the height of your career, have won awards, are leading a project, or have been promoted, but feel like a fraud, believing at any moment, someone will reveal you're not really all that good. Psychologists have long been intrigued by this distressing phenomenon, the impostor phenomenon. The roots of clinical psychology have led researchers to describe the impostor phenomenon as a personality trait that occurs in people who experience impostor feelings (for a recent review, see Bravata et al., 2019). Given the phenomenon reflects a negative and critical self-concept and has negative consequences for those suffering from it (Clance and Imes, 1978), the focus of the analysis has often been at the person level of the situation (e.g., Sonnak and Towell, 2001; McGregor et al., 2008). Because the impostor phenomenon occurs on the individual level, the effects and experiences also occur at this level.

Introduction

Suppose you are at the height of your career, have won awards, are leading a project, or have been promoted, but feel like a fraud, believing at any moment, someone will reveal you're not really all that good. Psychologists have long been intrigued by this distressing phenomenon, the impostor phenomenon. The roots of clinical psychology have led researchers to describe the impostor phenomenon as a personality trait that occurs in people who experience impostor feelings (for a recent review, see Bravata et al., 2019). Given the phenomenon reflects a negative and critical self-concept and has negative consequences for those suffering from it (Clance and Imes, 1978), the focus of the analysis has often been at the person level of the situation (e.g., Sonnak and Towell, 2001; McGregor et al., 2008). Because the impostor phenomenon occurs on the individual level, the effects and experiences also occur at this level.

For example, the term used to describe the impostor phenomenon displays this individualistic view. While Clance and Imes (1978) originally named the condition "impostor phenomena", the term "impostor syndrome" is used in academic research and popular culture to highlight the phenomenon's apparent individuality and dysfunction (e.g., Kets de Vries, 1990; Rohrmann et al., 2016; Bravata et al., 2019). The phenomenon is called a "syndrome"; this gives the impression that people who experience it are "patients" (Bravata et al., 2019, p. 1). This is highly problematic as it implies a medical framework of the individual's impairment (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; see also Kolligan and Sternberg, 1991).

The research on the phenomenon also demonstrates this individual experience of impostor sentiments. For example, this area of research has typically operationalised and measured the impostor phenomenon as a trait (rather than a state; Harvey, 1981; Clance, 1985; Mak et al., 2019). Further, studies have primarily focused on individuals to understand the causes and reasons of impostor sentiments. In this vein, researchers have pointed out personality traits (see Henning et al., 1998; Gibson-Beverly and Schwartz, 2008), attachment styles (see Sonnak and Towell, 2001), and perfectionistic tendencies (see Dudu, 2014) as the causes of impostor sentiments of individuals.

Importance of Context in Impostor Phenomenon

We argue that in order to fully understand the impostor phenomenon, it is important to complement the above-mentioned line of research at the individual level of analysis with a contextual view of impostor feelings (see also Heller et al., 2007). While the phenomenon is displayed at the level of an individual, making people feel as if they are not real, these people are not alone in the world. Rather, people's social environment plays a crucial role in influencing their self-perception (e.g., Tajfel and Turner, 1986; Hogg and Terry, 2000). We also think it is important to broaden the scope of impostor research to also consider the role of social context in explaining people's impostor feelings, given the extensive evidence from social psychology.

While Clance proposed that "interpersonal and social circumstances" might play a role in impostor feelings (Clance et al., 1995, p. 80), the social roots of this phenomena have yet to be given the theoretical and empirical attention they deserve by both scholars and practitioners. It seems particularly important to carefully examine contextual factors too - to gain a better understanding of the social foundations of this common phenomenon. We also explore how (a) the broader society and culture, (b) firms and other organisations, and (c) day-to-day social interactions and interpersonal relationships might play a significant role in the development of impostor sentiments, based on the decades of social-psychological research.

Societal and Cultural Influences

Several social-psychological studies have shown that a person's social status plays an important role in impostor sentiments, with individuals from lower social status facing certain challenges and concerns (Cokley et al., 2013; McClain et al., 2016; Chrousos et al., 2020; Chrousos and Mentis, 2020). Social-psychological studies reveal that groups often affected by impostor syndrome (women, ethnic minorities) are subject to negative stereotyping (Eagly et al., 2000; Eagly and Karau, 2002; Ellemers, 2018).

For instance, women are stereotyped as communal and warm but not leadership-oriented while men are stereotyped as leadership-oriented (Powell et al., 2002; Heilman, 2001). These stereotypes may make women feel uncomfortable or out of place in leadership roles, contributing to feelings of unworthiness (Heilman, 2012; Haynes and Heilman, 2013; Cokley et al., 2015). This may also account for contrasting evidence of gender differences in impostor feelings (Bravata et al., 2019).

Likewise, members of ethnic minorities are stereotyped as being unintelligent, or lazy, or less academically able (Reyna, 2000, 2008). Minority students may believe their achievements (such as being accepted by prestigious universities) is due to luck. Research shows that these students' experiences with racial discrimination lead to impostor feelings (Austin et al., 2009; Cokley et al., 2017; Bernard et al., 2018). In conclusion, impostor feelings are shaped by individual characteristics as well as group identity and social representation.

Institutional and Organizational Influences

Social and organisational psychology research highlights that institutional context, such as corporate organisations, educational institutions, or government bodies, significantly influence impostor feelings alongside broader societal factors. Women and ethnic minority employees are often under-represented in certain professions and leadership roles while over-represented in others (Catalyst, 2018). They frequently lack role models and may receive lower pay, which can lead them to question their suitability for particular positions (Lyness

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and Thompson, 2000; Catalyst, 2018; Peters et al., 2012). Consequently, these institutional structures may hinder a sense of belonging in environments historically dominated by white men, increasing the likelihood of experiencing impostor syndrome.

The way individuals are treated by colleagues and superiors also shapes impostor sentiments. Everyday interactions carry social cues that influence how people perceive their value and standing within a group (Smith et al., 1998; Huo and Binning, 2008; Lind and Tyler, 1988). Female and minority employees in male-dominated workplaces are often excluded from discussions or sought less for advice (Dovidio et al., 1986; Begeny et al., 2020), sending subtle messages that their contributions are undervalued, which can erode confidence and engagement (Holleran et al., 2011).

Thus, understanding the quality of interpersonal treatment is critical to comprehending impostor experiences. When people are consistently treated as if they are impostors, they are likely to internalize these feelings, whereas supportive treatment can mitigate them. From a human resource development perspective, this is particularly concerning, as employees experiencing impostor phenomena are often high-performing yet report greater emotional exhaustion and lower job satisfaction compared to their low-IP colleagues (Crawford, Shanine, Whitman, & Kacmar, 2016; Legassie et al., 2008; Neureiter & Traut-Mattausch, 2016). Understanding why impostor tendencies affect work outcomes can guide HRD professionals in developing strategies to help employees overcome barriers and realize their full potential (Demerouti, Bakker, & Leiter, 2014; Judge, Thoresen, Bono, & Patton, 2014).

Hypothesis

Impostor phenomenon will be positively associated with practice outcomes among employed people.

Method

Research Design

The research design is quantitative. It is an exploratory correlational survey-based study.

Participants

The population of interest chosen for the sample were males and females between 31 years (N=190). Convenience sampling was used for the participants. The sampling was drawn from the employees of various organisations in Karachi. Participants had diverse educational backgrounds, and were working in the professional area of medical health care, psychology and IT. item was properly explained to the participants individually in order was well explained to the participants personally to get responses. And responses were recorded on the questionnaire scales.

Inclusion criteria

The following categories of people were selected for the research:

The participants should be aged 21 to 31 years.

The participants should be without any severe or serious diseases.

The participants should be employed in professional careers of medical healthcare, psychology, and information technology.

The participants with the professional work experience of more than 6 months and 6 years.

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Exclusion criteria

The people who were not included in our study were,

Participants aged under 21 and above 31 years.

The participants who were working from home/working remotely or working in professions of medical health care, psychological and information technology.

The participants who had medical conditions

The participants who have less than 6 months and more than 6 years

Measures

Informed Consent

The aim of the study was described to the participants to allow them to provide informed consent after reading it. It was explained that the participants could withdraw from the study at any point in time. They were also informed of the confidentiality of the information.

Demographic Information Sheet

A demographic information sheet was administered to gather information on name, age, gender, socioeconomic background, educational background, occupation, date of joining current job, reason for changing job, and years of experience.

Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale (CIPS)

Pauline Rose Clance developed the Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale (CIPS) in 1985, which measures impostor feelings of lack of intelligence (Fake), the inability to internalise one's success (Discount) and the rationalisation that one has been lucky (Luck). It has a 5-point Likert format and shows a high level of internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.92$). The CIPS is highly correlated with the Perceived Fraudulence Scale (PFS; $r = 0.78$, $p \leq 0.01$). To demonstrate the discriminant validity of the CIPS, it was compared against measures of depression, self-esteem, self-monitoring and social anxiety. Results show that while there are some correlations between the Impostor Phenomenon (as measured by CIPS) and these other constructs, there are also significant differences. Research by Kertay et al. (1991) also supports the reliability and validity of the CIPS.

Schwartz Outcome Scale-10 (SOS-10)

The SOS-10 is a 10-item questionnaire developed by Mark A. Blais to measure well-being and mental health, and track change. It assesses interpersonal effectiveness, life satisfaction, optimism, positive self-appraisal and lack of psychiatric symptoms. The scale was designed for use with all types of patients, therapies and settings, with input from a wide range of senior clinicians and patients. The scale uses a 7-point scale (0-6) to score how the participant has felt over the last 7 days. Scores represent psychological health and well-being (higher scores) or emotional distress and poor psychological health (lower scores). The score ranges from 0 to 60, and can be obtained even when two items are missing by substituting the mean score. The test can be administered in computerised or paper-and-pencil format.

Ethical Considerations

As per the American Psychological Association (APA) code of ethics, the authors' consent for using the scales was sought via e-mail. The subjects were assured that data collected from them will be confidential. Initially, the informed consent was taken from all the participants, using a standard consent form. The participants were not obliged to participate in the study;

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they were allowed to withdraw from the study at their convenience. Participants were given a briefing about the study and its aim to avoid any biasness in the study's data.

Procedure

The participants from various organizations were required to sign the informed consent and demographic form. They were then asked to complete questionnaires of the Impostor Phenomenon and practice outcomes. The Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale and the Schwartz Outcome Scale data were entered into a web-based data entry system. The results were compared and a preliminary analysis was done to determine the impact of Impostor Phenomenon on practice outcomes.

Results

This chapter presents the statistical analysis of the research data collected for the current study, conducted through the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The reliability of the scales used was assessed: the Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale (CIPS) demonstrated good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .862$) and the Schwartz Outcome Scale-10 (SOS-10) showed acceptable reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = .770$). Descriptive statistics for both variables showed the mean scores, standard deviations, and acceptable ranges of skewness and kurtosis, indicating that the data were normally distributed. In addition, correlational analysis, regression analysis, and ANOVA were conducted to examine relationships and group differences among the study variables.

Correlational Analysis

Table 1

Correlation analysis between Impostor Phenomenon and Practice Outcomes.

		<i>CIPS</i>	<i>SOS</i>
<i>CIPS</i>	Pearson Correlation	1	-.356**
<i>SOS</i>	Pearson Correlation	-.356**	1

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .001$

The Pearson association between Practice Outcomes (SOS) and Impostor Phenomenon (CIPS) is shown in Table 1. The two variables have a substantial weak negative association, according to the data ($r = -.356$, $p < .01$). This suggests that practice outcome scores tend to decline as imposter phenomenon scores rise. To put it another way, people who feel more like imposters are more likely to report worse levels of overall psychological functioning, interpersonal effectiveness, life satisfaction, and well-being. Despite its weakness, the correlation's significance indicates a significant unfavorable relationship between the sample's practice outcomes and imposter encounters.

Regression Analysis

Table 2

Multiple linear regression showing Impostor Phenomenon as the predictor of Practice Outcomes.

<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R²</i>	ΔR^2	<i>F Change</i>	<i>df1</i>	<i>df2</i>	<i>Sig. F Change</i>
<hr/>							

1 .356a .127 .122 26.783 1 184 .000

Note: R² = R-squared, Δ R² = Adjusted R-Squared

The Pearson association between Practice Outcomes (SOS) and Impostor Phenomenon (CIPS) is shown in Table 2. The two variables have a substantial weak negative association, according to the data ($r = -.356$, $p < .01$). This suggests that practice outcome scores tend to decline as impostor phenomenon scores rise. To put it another way, people who feel more like imposters are more likely to report worse levels of overall psychological functioning, interpersonal effectiveness, life satisfaction, and well-being. Despite its weakness, the correlation's significance indicates a significant unfavorable relationship between the sample's practice outcomes and impostor encounters.

Analysis of Variance

Table 3

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for different groups of the study.

		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
CIPS	Between Groups	1326.088	2	663.044	4.026	.019
	Within Groups	30304.180	184	164.697		
	Total	31630.267	186			
SOS	Between Groups	361.303	2	180.651	2.065	.130
	Within Groups	16273.501	186	87.492		
	Total	16634.804	188			

The findings of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) used to evaluate group differences in CIPS and SOS scores are shown in Table 3. Results for the CIPS scores showed a statistically significant difference between groups ($F = 4.026$, $p = .019$), suggesting that levels of the impostor phenomenon differed significantly among the various study groups. SOS scores, on the other hand, did not substantially differ between groups ($F = 2.065$, $p = .130$), indicating that practice outcomes were not significantly different among the evaluated demographic categories. Together, these findings imply that although the impostor phenomenon varies at the group level, practice results are often consistent between groups.

Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between the Impostor Phenomenon and Practice Outcomes among working individuals, with a focus on determining whether impostor feelings significantly influence practice-related functioning. The findings of the study support the proposed relationship, indicating that the impostor phenomenon has a significant inverse association with practice outcomes.

Consistent with existing literature, individuals experiencing impostor feelings often struggle with perfectionism, procrastination, and self-doubt, all of which interfere with their work performance and ultimately influence practice outcomes such as organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviours. Individuals who experience impostor concerns may be restricted in their ability to fully develop their work potential (Neureiter & Traut-Mattausch, 2016). Prior research also indicates that feelings of impostorism reduce an

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individual's short-term ability to perform well at work and are associated with negative consequences for career success (Hadson, 2021). Further, individuals with impostor tendencies often avoid pursuing opportunities, thereby hindering their own potential (Chandra et al., 2019). Taken together, these findings suggest that impostor feelings can psychologically affect individuals in ways that disrupt their ability to work effectively and produce efficient outcomes.

Within the cultural context of the present study, previous research has indicated that women are more likely than men to experience impostor feelings, largely due to societal stereotypes portraying women as less intelligent, less capable, or less goal-oriented. Such stereotypes contribute to a higher prevalence of impostor tendencies in female populations (Rutaba et al., 2021). However, the current study found that males reported higher levels of impostor feelings than females, despite the sample having a slightly higher proportion of female participants (52.6%) compared to males (47.4%). This finding may reflect contextual, professional, or situational factors unique to the present sample.

The study also supports prior evidence that impostor phenomenon is more prevalent among individuals who have recently entered the workforce. Early career stages are often marked by major life transitions, heightened uncertainty, and increased pressure to perform. Individuals within their first several years of employment may be particularly vulnerable to impostor feelings due to dissatisfaction with work, fear of being exposed as incompetent, or excessive engagement in work tasks. For this reason, the sample included individuals with more than six months but less than six years of professional experience.

Practice outcomes in this study were assessed using the Schwartz Outcome Scale, which evaluates physical, psychological, and personal well-being. Previous research has highlighted that impostor feelings can increase stress levels, which may contribute to burnout. In line with this, the results of the current study indicate that impostor feelings negatively influence psychological and physical well-being. Individuals experiencing impostorism may continuously strive for perfectionism as a way to cope with stress, but this persistent pressure can increase burnout risk. Elevated stress, combined with constant workload demands, affects one's psychological and physical functioning. As the Schwartz Outcome Scale measures these dimensions, the findings suggest that impostor feelings may impair well-being, which in turn influences practice outcomes.

Overall, the findings of the present study reinforce the understanding that impostor phenomenon negatively affects working individuals by diminishing their well-being, increasing stress and burnout, and limiting their ability to achieve optimal practice outcomes.

Conclusion

This study examined the correlation between impostor phenomenon and practice outcomes among working individuals. According to the CIPS, 57% ($n = 108$) of the 190 participants experienced impostor feelings. Results showed a negative correlation ($r = -.356$) between impostor phenomenon and practice outcomes, indicating that higher impostor feelings are linked with lower scores on the Schwartz Outcome Scale. This suggests that self-doubt, perfectionism, and procrastination negatively affect individuals' work-related functioning. Additionally, participants from MBBS and IT fields reported higher impostor feelings than those in psychology, possibly due to greater psychological awareness among psychology professionals.

Limitations and Recommendations of the Study

This study has contributed valuable insights but also has several limitations. Firstly, the sample was limited to employees from Karachi working in medical healthcare, information technology, and psychology, which restricts generalization to the broader working population of Pakistan. Future research should include a larger, more diverse sample from different cities and various professions.

Secondly, the study focused on participants aged 21 to 31 years, limiting the applicability of results to other age groups. Expanding the age range in future studies would enhance generalizability. Thirdly, the sample included only male and female participants, with a higher proportion of females, preventing gender-based comparisons and limiting generalization to other gender identities, such as transgender individuals.

Another limitation is that the study did not examine the role of personality traits or mental health issues in the impostor phenomenon. Previous research indicates that pre-existing depression and anxiety are strong predictors of impostor feelings (Bernard et al., 2002; McGregor et al., 2008). Future research could explore organizational factors such as culture, training practices, and supervisor or coworker behaviors that contribute to the impostor phenomenon and practice outcomes. Additionally, studies could examine the impact of childhood experiences, including bullying or neglect, and interventions like workshops or training programs for students and employees to reduce impostor feelings. Research could also investigate which personality types (introvert, extrovert, or ambivert) are more vulnerable to impostor phenomenon and examine the role of self-concept, self-confidence, and attitudes toward learning and growth.

Lastly, comparative studies across different regions of Pakistan and internationally could provide a broader understanding of impostor phenomenon and its relationship with mental health, personality traits, and practice outcomes.

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